

**Improving the technology for producing energy-saving building ceramics
from local raw materials.**

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Abstract: This article talks about energy efficiency, energy-saving insulating materials, modern building materials and their rational use, improving the technology for producing energy-saving building ceramics from local raw materials.

Key words: energy efficiency, energy resources, insulating material, heat insulator, transparent structures, energy-saving materials.

Energy efficiency means efficient use of energy. The energy saving potential is very important for the whole world and Karakalpakstan in particular.

About 40% of the world's energy consumption is used in buildings. They are the main consumers of energy and the main sources of greenhouse gas emissions. 2/3 of this energy is spent on heating and air purification, and modern technologies can significantly reduce this figure.

Modern trends and prospects for the construction and reconstruction of buildings are associated, first of all, with a rational approach to the use of energy resources, a comfortable indoor microclimate and a reduction in environmental impact.

The main result of increasing requirements for thermal protection of enclosing structures has been the transition to multi-layer structural solutions. They make it

possible to achieve high heat transfer resistance without increasing the thickness of surrounding structures due to the effect of effective insulation.

Various thermal insulation materials and structures, energy-saving facade systems, monolithic housing construction technologies and energy-saving transparent structures were used in the construction.

The most effective heat insulator in construction is air. The main difference in the heat-saving properties of building materials is the ratio of the volume of air spaces to the volume of the frame frame that forms these openings. In this case, a characteristic relationship is observed between the thermal conductivity of the material, its specific gravity and its strength properties. In addition, air can be an independent layer of insulation in multi-layer walls.

Materials with significant heat-shielding properties are a priority in the construction market.

Thermally efficient silica granite building block is made from a building material with high energy-saving qualities and durability. This block is a layer cake in which the first layer is responsible for the load-bearing capacity of the wall, the next is an effective insulation, the next layer is a support layer and simultaneously performs several functions:

- works well for insulation;
 - corresponds to the load-bearing capacity of the wall;
 - serves as the basis for the outer finishing layer.
- And the last layer is various decorative coatings.

Thermally efficient building block. Reducing the consumption of fuel and energy resources is especially important when using brick buildings. The experiments carried out made it possible to develop the main directions for achieving a high level

of quality of thermal protection without increasing the thickness of external brick walls. World construction practice shows that the construction of external walls from facing bricks and large-format ceramic blocks is the most advanced technical and energy-saving solution. This ensures high levels of strength and stability of buildings, as well as a high level of heat retention. This creates not only optimal temperature, humidity and hygienic conditions inside buildings, but also an air exchange regime inside the walls. The quality characteristics of porous brick are associated with its structure with many microscopic air spaces, which provide the brick with excellent thermal insulation properties.

The following are most often used as heat insulators in façade design solutions:

- mineral wool thermal insulation boards;
- extruded polyethylene foam;
- heat-insulating slabs made of basalt rocks;
- foam glass slabs (blocks), etc.

Heat loss through windows reaches up to 50% of the total heat loss through building envelopes. Therefore, the most important task of energy saving in buildings is to improve the heat-insulating properties of transparent closed structures, primarily windows.

The modern building materials industry produces a variety of energy-saving glass: Energy-saving glass has a number of advantages:

- reflects long-wave heat rays to its emitter (in winter into an apartment with heating devices, and in summer outside with sun-heated stones, asphalt, etc.), which reduces costs. heating in winter and air conditioning in summer;
- has a high thermal insulation ability;

- reduces the possibility of condensation forming on the glass, since the temperature on the surface of the glass unit is higher than on the surface of ordinary glass;
- prevents tarnishing of floor coverings and interior items.

The operational energy efficiency of buildings is determined, first of all, by their thermal and energy efficiency, which, in turn, depends on the thermal insulation properties of the transparent parts of the outer shell of the building.

Increasing the energy efficiency of buildings is only possible through the use of integrated architectural and construction solutions.

The design potential for energy saving in buildings and structures largely depends on the experience and qualifications of the project authors; the real potential depends on the quality of construction work and the correctness of design decisions at the construction stage.

The market for energy-efficient building materials is very wide, but their choice should be based on thermal calculations and design and planning solutions for energy saving in buildings.

The use of modern energy-efficient structures and materials makes it possible to create buildings not only with low energy consumption, but also with different indicators of the price range, comfort and environmental friendliness, which is certainly relevant in the modern construction industry.

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